

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF LOW COST ON FARM COOLING STORAGE STRUCTURE

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Abstract

Most of the horticultural crops including fruits and vegetables begin to deteriorate shortly after harvest. Refrigerated cool storage is considered to be the best method of storing fruits and vegetables. However, this method is not only highly energy intensive but also involves huge capital investment. The present trend world over is to develop a simple low cost cooling system for storage of fruits and vegetables. In order to overcome the problem of on farm storage, low cost environment friendly on farm cooling structure is needed to be developed. The overall dimensions of the on farm cooling storage structure were 2.4 × 2.4 × 2.4 m it works on principal of evaporative cooling. On farm cooling storage structure consisted of main frame, used cellulose pad as a cooling medium, turbo ventilator, exhaust fan for removal of warm air and covered with MS sheets. Tomato, cucumber, okra, and capsicum are kept inside of the structure and performance of the structure was tested. The structure was constructed and evaluated in field. It was found that suitable environment of about 15-20°C lower temperature than the outside ambient could be maintained inside the structure and cooling efficiency of 82 and 92% was found for on farm cooling storage structure. Considering the above, to provide appropriate atmosphere as well as suitable environment to the produce for on-farm storage of perishables, the research was proposed to develop a low cost on farm cooling storage structure using evaporative cooling principle for horticultural produce in order avoid losses of perishable produce occurring instantly after harvest.

Keyword: Horticultural crops, evaporative cooling, cooling storage structure, performance

Introduction

Post-harvest losses of fruits and vegetables remain a critical challenge in global agriculture, particularly in developing countries where inadequate storage infrastructure limits farmers' ability to preserve perishable produce. Globally, approximately 1.3 billion tons of food roughly one-third of all food produced for human consumption is lost or wasted annually, with post-harvest losses in sub-Saharan Africa estimated between 30% to 50% before reaching final consumers (Makule *et al.*, 2022). These losses are primarily attributed to poor post-harvest handling practices and the absence of effective cold storage facilities, resulting in significant economic losses for smallholder farmers and exacerbated food insecurity (Balogun *et al.*, 2025).

Temperature and relative humidity control are the key factors in extending the shelf-life of perishable commodities. Conventional refrigeration-based cold storage systems maintain optimal storage conditions but involve high initial investment (Rs. 5–7 lakhs/tonne) and substantial operating costs (up to 4 kW·h energy requirement per tonne), making them inaccessible to small and medium-scale farmers. These barriers have intensified the need for affordable, energy-efficient, and locally adaptable cooling storage alternatives that can operate in rural and resource-constrained environments (Anonymous, 2026). Refrigerated storage is widely recognized as the most effective method for keeping fruits and vegetables fresh, yet it is highly energy-intensive and requires substantial capital investment. Moreover, it is impractical for rural or on-farm settings where producers need to store commodities for only a few days to accumulate enough quantities before transporting them to distant urban markets. The availability of power and its associated costs present significant challenges, making refrigerated storage unsuitable for short-term, on-farm storage purposes. Consequently, there is a growing shift in focus from conventional cold storage toward alternative storage systems. Maintaining lower temperatures within an enclosed chamber has become critically important, particularly under Indian conditions. Evaporative cooled storage represents one such alternative that has been extensively researched and offers a viable solution (Kapilan and Kumar, 2023).

Evaporative cooling offers widespread applications, from providing comfort cooling in residential, commercial, agricultural, and institutional buildings to modern uses such as spot cooling in power plants and foundries. This principle is particularly common in greenhouses. Evaporative cooling is a physical process where an object or fluid is

cooled through the evaporation of a liquid into the surrounding air that contacts it. Water evaporation produces a powerful cooling effect, with faster evaporation resulting in greater cooling. This method is highly suitable for short-term storage of fruits and vegetables (Chaudhari *et al.*, 2015). It is efficient and cost-effective for reducing temperature and increasing relative humidity, represents a proven and reliable system, is environmentally friendly, and can be operated without specialized skills. Therefore, evaporative cooling can be considered a viable alternative to help reduce postharvest losses in fresh produce experienced by farmers in India, provided that cheaper energy sources are found to power the cooling system using locally available materials (FAO, 1983).

Evaporative cooled storage structure has turned out to be useful for short term, on-farm storage of fruits and vegetables in hot and dry regions. Evaporative cooling is an efficient and economical means for reducing temperature and increasing the relative humidity of an enclosure, and has been extensively tried for improving the shelf life of horticultural produce which is essential for maintaining the freshness of the commodities. Evaporative cooling is an environmental friendly air conditioning system that works utilizing induced processes of heat and mass transfer where air and water are working fluids (Vala *et al.*, 2016). Such a system provides an inexpensive, energy efficient, environment friendly and potentially attractive cooling system (Basediya *et al.*, 2013). Considering the above, to provide appropriate atmosphere as well as suitable environment to the produce for on-farm storage of perishables, the research work was proposed to develop a low cost on farm cooling storage to provide optimum temperature and humidity conditions for storing perishable agricultural produce, thereby reducing post-harvest losses, enhancing food security, and improving income stability for small-scale farmers.

Material and Method**Theoretical considerations**

The following factors were considered while developing On Farm Cooling Storage Structure

1. Suitability of structure for storage of perishable crops.
2. Minimum storage losses.
3. Easy of operation and maintenance.
4. Low cost of erection, operation and maintenance.

Construction materials

Structure Frame, cooling wall material (woodwool, khus and cellulose), roof, water circulation unit, exhaust fan and turbo ventilator.

Results and Discussion

Design Criteria

Design of storage system

The capacity of the storage system was determined using equation (Halliday *et al.*, 2014).

$$\begin{aligned} V &= L \times B \times H \\ &= 8 \times 8 \times 8 \\ &= 2.438 \times 2.438 \times 2.438 \\ &= 14.49 \text{ m}^3 \end{aligned}$$

Design and Selection of Suction Fan

The determination of fan capacity was in accordance with Bartok, 2013 as given in equation below.

Fan capacity: 8 cfm / sqft x Floor area in sqft (cfm) = cubic feet per minute)

$$\text{Floor area} = 8 \times 8 = 64 \text{ sqft} = 1920 \text{ cm}^2 = 1.92 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{Therefore, fan capacity} = 8 \times 64 = 502 \text{ cfm}$$

Factor of safety is 10% of fan capacity given as:

$$F_s = 502 \times 0.10 = 50.2 \text{ cfm}$$

$$\text{Required fan capacity} = \text{Fan capacity} + \text{Factor of safety}$$

$$= 502 + 50.2 = 552.2 \text{ cfm}$$

Hence, 9 inch (225 mm) exhaust fan having air flow of 500 cfm was selected.

Structure Frame

The main frame of the on farm cooling storage structure was made of galvanized iron GI Channels (50 mm), with locking and unlocking arrangement for easy assembling of the structure when in use and easy dismantling of the structure when not in use.

Cooling Wall Material

Appropriate three types of cooling pad materials were selected and used based on the literature reviewed. Laboratory models of three types of storage structure having different materials such as woodwool, khus and cellulose material as cooling pad were manufactured using mild steel angle sections (25 x 25 x 1 mm) as shown in Fig 1. The walls of the structure were made by cutting the appropriate size of cellulose pad and fixing over the frame from all the four sides. The other type of walls of the structure was fabricated from mild steel wire mesh with wood wool and khus material fixed over the frame of the structure. The top of the structure was covered with galvanized iron sheet. The fan/ turbo ventilator was provided on the roof.

Fig 1. On Farm Cooling Structure Models

Roof

Roof of the structure is made up of galvanized iron sheet (GI) fitted with hitlon sheet from the inside of the structure in order to avoid the heating and temperature rise inside the structure.

Water Circulation

Water cycle of the evaporative cooling system consisted of a tank of volume (75 lit/h i.e. 600 lit/day) 600 litres. A 0.3 kW centrifugal pump having maximum discharge of 27 lit/min and maximum head of 12 m was used. PVC pipe having 25 mm diameter. Water is pumped from the tank to the mid-length of the distributor through perforated PVC pipe. Waterfalls freely from the distributor onto the pad. Water flow through the cooling pad and falls freely on to the gutter. The gutter is slightly inclined and ends above the water tank. Cellulose pad work on a simple principle of cooling with the help of water. Water flow from top to bottom of the pad and the air is sucked through the cellulose where the air cools down with the help of water, thus the warm air cools down and thus cools the temperature inside the structure. The water distribution system was fitted on the top of this frame and the water was distributed over the upper face of the evaporative pad by a tube, with many holes to drip the water evenly onto the pad face. The pipe was made of PVC, 25 mm in diameter and had 2 mm diameter holes drilled on 50 mm distance along the top of the distribution pipe. Pad was continuously kept wetted.

Exhaust Fan

A negative pressure is needed to be created inside the structure which is a function of the pad and the fan, when this happens, air at a positive pressure rushes into the system through the pad. For proper air circulation, and the best desired airflow pattern, the fan was located at the central position at the top which now allows air to be drawn from the pad area which in turn draws the cool air and expel the humidified air out. Evaporative air cooling use very little energy, but most of used for the fan. The axial- flow exhaust fan was fixed at the top of on farm cooling storage structure to control the relative humidity and reduce concentration of carbon dioxide released by stored produce inside the storage structure.

Turbo Ventilator

The turbo ventilator works on the principal of natural convection that works to pull the warm air from the structure from lower position commonly through vents. This rotation gives rise to the centrifugal force which creates vaccum inside of the structure. The turbo ventilators (dia. 30 cm) were provided at two sides of the fan which were needed to withdraw the warm air during the night hours when the fan was kept switched off. The construction material and specifications are given in table 1. and the details drawing of the developed structure are shown in fig 2. and the complete structure is shown in fig 3.

Fig 2. Isometric views of On Farm Cooling Storage Structure

Fig 3. Developed On Farm Cooling Storage Structure

Table 1: Construction Material and their specifications

Sr. No.	Name of parts	Material used	Specifications
1.	Structure Frame	GI channel	2.4 × 2.4 × 2.4 m = 13.824 cu.m
2.	Sidewall	Cooling pads	3.6 sq.m (19 nos.)
3.	Top Surface	Mild steel covered with hitlon sheets from inside	4.8 sq.m (3 nos.)

4.	Turbo ventilator	Stainless steel	30 cm diameter (2 nos.)
5.	Exhaust fan	-	1350 RPM

Conclusion

Laboratory models of three types of storage structure having different materials such as woodwool, khus pad and cellulose material as cooling pad were manufactured. The structure and operational parameters were optimized and the performance evaluation of the structure was also studied on the basis of different response parameters such as cooling efficiency and storage losses. On the basis of experimental trials, the cellulose pad structure was found to have better water holding capacity and maximum cooling efficiency compared to other two materials. Also, the storage losses during trials in laboratory models were found to be minimum using cellulose pad cooling storage structure. The testing of on farm cooling storage structure shows that the shelf life for perishables stored inside the On Farm Cooling Storage Structure was 4-5 days more in case of tomato and cucumber and 3-4 days more for capsicum and okra, compared to room/ambient storage.

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